

context when taking part in therapeutic modalities such as art therapy , horticultural therapy, journaling, music therapy, movement. Expression through creative arts or expressive therapies can take place in a one-on-one setting with one therapist or in a group setting with many therapists. Each modality supplies a different medium or format in which people can safely communicate their core ideas and feelings to one another. Non-verbal processes and products (artwork, musical expression, movement sequences, writing, etc.) can serve as a visual or written record of the experiences of the inner system of alternative identities, and these records can be examined at any point. Expressive therapies are especially helpful in the healing process because vital information about current stressors, triggers, safety issues, earlier traumatic experiences, and coping strategies are often spoken nonverbally long before they are voiced. This makes expressive therapies particularly useful. Following this, various artworks, writings, musical compositions, etc., are available to aid in working towards a variety of different therapeutic goals. A discussion about it can be used.

Keywords: *EMDR, DID, Psychological Therapies, Psychological Disorders, Psychological Illnesses, Dissociative identity disorder, DID*

1. Introduction

When used in conjunction with verbal associations, nonverbal psychotherapeutic approaches help to bridge the communication gap between the patient's inner and outer world, as well as between the disconnected parts of the patient's self. Additionally, in both group and individual settings, expressive therapy helps patients develop focus, fact-based thinking, internal organization and cooperation, problem-solving abilities, and their ability to use restraint strategies. Creative therapies have the potential to improve insight, glorification of anger and other strong emotions, and working through traumatic events. In addition, creative therapies can help with the goal of integration . In addition to the role, they play in illuminating diagnostic concerns, many psychotherapists find patients' drawings and diaries useful in ongoing psychotherapy sessions with these patients. One of the standard art assessments often used when trying to make a differential diagnosis of dissociative identity disorder (DID) is called the Diagnostic Drawing Series. This

series of drawings was developed by Cohen, Mills and Kijak (1994). It has also been determined that it can be used especially in people who are dissociative (Mills & Cohen, 1993). For people diagnosed with DID, rehabilitation treatments such as occupational therapy , horticultural therapy, and therapeutic recreation can be extremely effective in improving overall functioning. The patient's ability to perform activities reliably and age appropriately is documented through the provision of organized, reality-based crafts or tasks alongside regular functional assessments.

2. Various Interventions

Various interventions include working with alternative identities and problem solving during processing (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Forgash & Knipe , 2008; Gelinias , 2003, 2009; Paulsen , 2008, 2009; Twombly & Schwartz, 2008); Korn International Society for the Study of Trauma and Dissociation and Leeds(2002) Resource Development and Installation (Gelinias , 2003); using protocols to re-establish today's orientation and security (Knipe , 2009; Twombly , 2009a, 2009b); integrating hypnotic techniques into EMDR protocols to maintain stabilization (Fine & Berkowitz , 2001; Twombly , 2000, 2005); and using EMDR for “safe place” work, helping to develop many concepts related to developing tolerance for emotions and sensations, and fostering internal cooperation between alternative identities. The coping skills learned through these interventions are used initially to aid stabilization and eventually to help in the management of processing particularly terrifying traumatic memories. When collaborating with patients with dissociative identity disorder (DID), it is necessary to take measures to overcome and reduce the likelihood of overflowing dissociative barriers. Van der Hart et al. (2006) noted that " The inherent risk of using EMDR in chronically traumatized individuals is that it often reactivates too many traumatic memories too quickly." This is a risk that comes with using EMDR with people who have been traumatized for a long time . Associative processing, which is the act of allowing the process to bridge with associated memories, is not encouraged in DID patients, unlike the typical EMDR procedure . This is done to keep the material quantity and material density at a manageable level. Instead, target memory should be procedurally isolated to the greatest extent possible. Various techniques have been developed to modulate the intensity of EMDR work , such as piecemeal abreaction and serial desensitization , which involve processing various aspects of a memory held by discrete eigenstates . Other protective modifications of EMDR for DID include pacing and an

alternative type of bilateral stimulation in highly dissociative patients . These changes are aimed at reducing the risk of adverse effects. Many medical professionals believe that the use of alternating auditory or tactile dual stimulation as well as shorter sets of alternative dual stimulation (Lazrove & Fine , 1996; Paulsen , 1995; Wesselman , 2000) may be better tolerated by dissociative patients.

Assessments in occupational therapy can also supply information about ways in which dissociative symptoms can have a negative impact on activities of daily living, such as keeping personal hygiene , preparing meals, managing finances, working, going to school, spending free time or being unstructured . Most expressionist and rehabilitation therapists who work in inpatient, partial, inpatient, and outpatient settings have expert's or doctoral degrees and are board-certified and/or registered in their field. Additionally, these therapists may hold licenses in mental health fields. However, the formal use of expressive and rehabilitation therapies should only be practiced by clinicians with proper training and certification. Sensory-motor Experiential Psychotherapy The multitude of symptoms that affect touch, perception, autonomic control, and motility make the treatment of dissociative identity disorder (DID) difficult. Traditional speech therapy approaches are combined with body-centered therapies in sensorimotor psychotherapy. These interventions are aimed directly at trauma-related neurobiological and somatoform dissociation symptoms (Ogden et al ., 2006). Direct somatic therapies help the patient regain the ability to manage disordered bodily states that lead to dissociation. These situations result from the dissociation of the patient. Sensori-motor psychotherapy is essentially integrative and prevents iatrogenic worsening of personality dissociation. This is because one's body is a common whole for all identities.

Paying attention to how the body moves and feels can both educate the therapist about the client's history of traumatic experiences and introduce them to the physical postures, gestures, and emotions unique to each identity, while also supplying opportunities to break these patterns. sensorimotor that alerts the patient to somatic and physiological indicators of change Therapies are often the first signs of change and can be extremely helpful in helping the patient gain control over the change. For the use of sensorimotor psychotherapy in the treatment of phase-oriented trauma for ICD , it is necessary to understand how to intervene at the bodily level for each phase of treatment. This includes teaching somatic skills to ease stability and symptom reduction in Stage

1, keeping the patient's general balance while trying to complete actions and integrating traumatic memory in Stage 2, and teaching physical actions that promote greater integration and adaptation in normal life.

3. Directed Awareness

Sensory-motor psychotherapy with an emphasis on the use of "directed awareness" can aid in the restoration of a witnessing self and ultimately assist patients in identifying attributes of identities present in the here and now. Sensory-motor psychotherapy, unlike most body-centered therapies, allows the practice of physical touch as an option, but it is not an inherently "firsthand" approach. As a result, it is suitable for use with clients suffering from dissociative disorder and is easy to incorporate into more traditional psychotherapeutic models. Because of the severe anxiety that many people with DID have about their own bodies and physical contact with other people, this method should be used with caution and at the proper time. Clinicians, sensorimotor Before trying to apply therapy techniques, they must ensure that they have a thorough understanding of the phase-oriented paradigm of DID treatment. Electroconvulsive Therapy (ECT) Although ECT has not been shown to be an effective or acceptable treatment for dissociative disorders, it may be helpful in treating a comorbid refractory condition.

overlaid on DID (Bowman & Coons, 1992; DeBattista, Solvason, & Spiegel, 1998)—also known as double depression, which describes a major depressive episode consistently superimposed on a depressive base. (Bowman and Coons, 1992; DeBattista, Solvason, and Spiegel, 1998) (Klein, Taylor, Harding, and Dickstein, 1988). In cases of double depression caused by ICD, the presence of melancholy and/or true psychotic symptoms is a better indicator of how well ECT will work. Like other patients undergoing ECT, a subset of DID patients report significant permanent autobiographical memory loss and persistent memory impairment after ECT. This memory impairment is superimposed (and can be difficult to distinguish) on chronic complex dissociative amnesia.

ECT patients also report significant permanent autobiographical memory loss. Electroconvulsive for dissociative identity disorder (DID) Informed consent for therapy (ECT) should address these challenges in addition to the informed consent considerations typical for ECT. In the past, prior to

the development of clinical and psychometric assessment tools, hypnosis and/or pharmacologically eased interviews (most commonly using amobarbital (Amytal)) were used to aid in the diagnosis and treatment of dissociative disease. These interviews have also been used for the differential diagnosis and treatment of acute conversion disorders and diffuse dissociative amnesia, among other things (Naples & Hackett , 1978). However, the use of amobarbital and other pharmaceuticals with comparable properties may pose a risk to the health of some people. Some of the possible side effects of these drugs include drowsiness, hypotension, loss of coordination and allergic responses. Pharmacologically assisted interviews are classified as "conscious sedation", according to current criteria set by the Joint Commission on the Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations in the United States . For this reason, these treatments can only be performed within the boundaries of the hospital, which is equipped with the necessary monitoring and safety standards used by the anesthesia department of the hospital. It is possible that administrative norms in other countries are different in this regard, but even if they are different, these processes are still unusual outside the United States.

As a result, pharmacologically assisted interviews are not currently often used in the diagnostic or therapeutic processes of dissociative identity disorder (DID). One type of dissociative disorder is known as dissociative identity disorder (DID), once called multiple personality disorder. Many people with dissociative identity disorder had a difficult upbringing that may have caused them to leave their bodies as a way of coping with the tremendous trauma they had experienced. Presence of at least two separate personalities is one of the symptoms of dissociative identity disorder (DID). Other symptoms include feeling disconnected from the person's sense of self. Memory loss is a common symptom of dissociative identity disorder (DID), which occurs when different people take control . DID is one of the most misunderstood conditions in the field of psychiatry. To raise awareness and reduce the associated social stigma, it is essential to dispel common misconceptions about this condition by citing reliable studies. There is a common misconception that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is not a real illness but a temporary "medical fad."

On the other hand, DID has been documented for hundreds of years and has a prominent place in the relevant medical literature . The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th edition (DSM-5), classifies dissociative disorders such as DID as one of their categories. Patients with this condition may have two or more separate personality states coexisting within the same

physical body. These identities may have different names, features, voices and behaviors. Memory loss is a common symptom of dissociative identity disorder (DID) . According to research conducted and published in 2014, dissociative identity disorder is a complex but real disease that can be shown to exist in many different indicators. According to Trusted Sources Studies, DID is associated with various brain areas as well as cognitive abilities. It is not difficult to distinguish the symptoms of DID from the symptoms of other disorders. The illness is often linked to acute emotional trauma in early relationships. As a result of the decline after the increase in the number of diagnoses during the 1980s and 1990s , dissociative identity disorder (DID) became a medical fad. Some people feel that it was once widespread practice to diagnose people with this condition and that at some point it went out of style. However, cases of DID have been reported in the medical literature for hundreds of years, according to the findings of Trusted Source researchers. In addition, experts reported that 1,339 research publications on DID were made between 2000 and 2014. This means that professionals' interest in the disease continues. Other evidence to contradict this misconception includes Patients diagnosed with DID are reliably found in inpatient, outpatient, and community samples collected from around the world. The diagnosis of DID can be made with an elevated level of accuracy through clinical practice as well as structured or semi-structured interviews. Psychotherapy that addresses trauma and dissociation is often helpful for those with dissociative identity disorder (DID). DID is relatively easily distinguishable from various other mental health conditions. Both borderline personality disorder (BPD) and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are possible conditions that co-occur with dissociative identity disorder (DID) (PTSD).

The myth that DID is a relatively rare disease The belief that DID is a relatively rare condition is common and can even be found in some introductory psychology texts. It may seem otherwise, based on prevalence statistics in both the general population and psychiatric settings. In fact, DID is much more common than schizophrenia. According to Research 's findings, DID is found in approximately 1.1% to 1.5% of population samples. In contrast, 0.25% to 0.64% of adults are believed to suffer from schizophrenia. Of a sample population of 658 people from New York, 1.5% met the diagnostic criteria for DID. In a study conducted on 628 community women in Turkey, 1.1% of them were found to have IPD. Studies examining communities exposed to unusually elevated levels of trauma or cultural oppression reveal that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is the most common. For example, in a highly traumatic inner-city sample in the United

States, 6% of multiple hospital admissions were diagnosed with DID. 3. The myth that dissociative identity disorder and schizophrenia are the same thing Contrary to popular assumption, dissociative identity disorder and schizophrenia are two separate mental illnesses. The belief that a person with schizophrenia has a "split personality"—the concept that the self is split into several identities—continues to be a common but inaccurate misconception about the disorder. A 2008 survey by the National Alliance on Mental Illness (NAMI) showed that 64 percent of respondents thought "split or multiple personalities" were signs of schizophrenia. Recent attempts at mental health have tried to educate people on the distinction between the two, but the misconception persists. The fact that DID symptoms often overlap with positive symptoms of schizophrenia, such as altered sense of reality, is another factor that contributes to perpetuating this misconception. But people with DID are much less likely to have the negative symptoms of schizophrenia, such as withdrawal from social situations or an inability to enjoy activities they previously enjoyed . People with schizophrenia have a lower risk of experiencing dissociative symptoms, such as forgetting who they are and losing their memories. This is an added critical difference. Schizophrenia is an inherited disorder that usually runs in families and, if left untreated, can lead to a sustained decline in a person's level of functioning. Schizophrenia is a disease that can also be inherited. Trauma is the most common trigger of dissociative identity disorder (DID), rather than genetics.

4. DID May Cause a Personality Problem

Dissociative identity disorder (DID), contrary to widespread belief, is not a personality problem. The DSM-5 classifies dissociative disorder (DID) as a dissociative disorder. People may have this misconception that DID is a personality disorder for several varied reasons. Despite being renamed dissociative identity disorder in 1994, some people still refer to the condition as "multiple personality disorder." This can lead to misunderstandings. Another explanation is that those who suffer from borderline personality disorder are more likely to have DID . Although both diseases have common symptoms (as with many diseases), they can be distinguished from each other due to the unique characteristics of each. Memory interruptions and a general feeling of disconnection from one's body and the outside world are symptoms associated with dissociative disorders . Personality disorders are characterized by a recurring pattern of traits that impair an individual's ability to live a normal life. The association between DID , the myth that people with DID are

more likely to be aggressive, and an increase in violent behavior has not been conclusively proved by research. Horror movies featuring characters with dissociative identity disorder (DID) have helped perpetuate this misconception and can even be blamed for starting it. The diagnosis of DID is controversial because of the idea that criminals who claim to have DID will not be punished if they claim that another person has committed the crime, according to research by the Trusted Source in 2009. However, there is no association between DID and an increase in criminal activity. Participants were minimally involved in the legal system, according to the findings of a 2017 study of 173 patients treated for dissociative identity disorder by a trusted source. The findings of the study showed that only 0.6% of the population had been imprisoned during the previous six months. In addition, there have been no reports of convictions or probation in the previous six months. As a result, they concluded that none of the DID symptoms accurately predicted criminal activity. The misconception that people with dissociative identity disorder (DID) pose a threat contributes to the persistent stigma of people with the condition. To review, dissociative identity disorder (DID) is an often-misunderstood mental condition. The stigma experienced by many living with DID can be partially alleviated by removing common beliefs. A better understanding of dissociative identity disorder (DID) and the reduction of the stigma associated with it could lead to an increase in the number of people living with DID who feel comfortable seeking help or pursuing treatment, which could ultimately result in a life more satisfactory and stable. The diagnosis of dissociative identity disorder (DID) is generally considered to be the most challenging of all psychiatric disorders. Getting a diagnosis for many completely mismatched conditions is one of the "clues" to dissociative identity disorder (DID).

One of the most severe forms of dissociative disorders is dissociative identity disorder (DID). Dissociative disorder is diagnosed when an individual's dissociative tendency becomes a persistent reaction to one or more traumatic experiences. DID is a condition in which a person's identity is split between two or more personality states, commonly known as alters. This condition was once known as multiple personality disorder. Added common symptoms may include:

- dissociative amnesia

Memory problems not caused by any known medical condition. Dissociative fugue is a mental state in which a person travels aimlessly and is unable to remember their own personal information.

Feeling that the person's identity is confused Ninety percent of those with DID have been the target of systematic abuse or neglect during their developmental years, according to the APA.

5. symptoms

One of the reasons that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is so difficult to diagnose is that many of the symptoms overlap with other illnesses.

Prazosin is a drug that helps in the treatment of hypervigilance and night terrors. Individuals suffering from dissociative identity disorder are among the troubled people. People with dissociative identity disorder can sometimes suffer from dissociative fugue, such as when they learn they have traveled but do not remember that they have traveled. The extent to which they are aware of their forgetfulness varies from person to person, and it is common for people with dissociative identity disorder to underestimate the impact of their amnesic symptoms , even though the memory loss is obvious to others and can cause them suffering . Property statuses are an accepted element of the religious or cultural practices of a sizable part of the world's population. Manifestations of possessive-like identities often take the form of actions controlled by a ghost or other supernatural creature. But when possessions are unwelcome, cause discomfort or deterioration, and are not considered a normal part of cultural or religious practice, it can escalate to the level of a mental illness. According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition , more than seventy percent of people with dissociative identity disorder (DID) have tried suicide at least once, and self-harming behavior is common among this group. Treatment is essential to improve the quality of life of those with DID and to avoid suicide attempts.

6. Reasons

It is not fully understood what causes some people to develop dissociative identity disorder; however, a common contributing factor is that they report being the victim of severe physical and sexual abuse as children. It is possible at any age to show the first signs of the disease. People with dissociative identity disorder are more likely to suffer from post-traumatic symptoms such as

nightmares, flashbacks or startle reactions, as well as post-traumatic stress disorder . Dissociative identity disorder is more common in close biological relatives of individuals with the disorder than in the general population, according to the findings of several studies. In the past, this disorder was rarely reported; however, the diagnosis is becoming more common and controversial. Because people with dissociative identity disorder are extremely suggestible, there is a school of thought among some professionals that their symptoms are at least somewhat iatrogenic ; that is, they were brought up by questioning their therapists. On the other hand, studies using neuroimaging have supplied evidence of identity shifts.

What Other Conditions Are Classified as Dissociative Disorders?

There are a variety of dissociative disorders, each of which focuses on a person's disconnection from the world around them. For example, a person suffering from dissociative amnesia has difficulty remembering important personal information about themselves, such as who they are, where they live, and other similar details. Also, a person with depersonalization or derealization disorder distances themselves from their own behavior. Treatment Long-term psychotherapy, with the aim of deconstructing the different personalities and integrating them into a single personality, is the main treatment for dissociative identity disorder. Cognitive therapy and creative therapy are two added types of therapy. Antidepressants, anti-anxiety medications, or tranquilizers may be prescribed to help control the psychological symptoms associated with this disorder. However, there are no medications that specifically treat this disorder. Many people disabled by DID experience an improvement in their ability to function in both their professional and personal lives after receiving proper treatment. In 1988, Dell¹ conducted a survey asking clinicians about the responses they received from patients and other people because of their interest in dissociative identity disorder (DID), formerly known as multiple personality disorder. More than eighty percent of the 62 participants who treated patients with DID say they had "moderate to extreme" reactions from their colleagues. These responses included attempts by their patients to refuse hospitalization or to force their patients to be discharged, even patients whom respondents considered to be at serious risk of committing suicide .

- a. *Dell hypothesized that the emotional responses to the diagnosis of IPD were the result of the anxiety brought on by the "strange, disturbing clinical presentation"*¹

of the condition, comparable to the emotional responses of some doctors to psychiatric emergency patients.

- b. Another factor contributing to the intense debate surrounding the diagnosis of DID is disagreement over the importance of observable symptoms :*

dissociative identity disorder a condition in which some doctors do not exist, a distinct and subtle collection of core symptoms and behaviors?

The fear that offenders will "escape" from punishment by a pure justice system that attributes the behavior to another personality and does not hold the perpetrator accountable is the third and most important reason for discussion. People fear that criminals will "escape" without punishment. Diagnosing DID is not without its detractors. Cases of DID such as those reported by Franke , Ganaway , and McHugh , among others, have instead been attributed to social contagion, hypnotic suggestion, and misdiagnosis. ("Dissociative Identity Disorder - PMC - PubMed Central (PMC)") These authors claimed that people diagnosed with dissociative identity disorder are highly hypnotizable and, as a result, incredibly open to suggestions. They argue that these patients are likely to follow direct or implicit hypnotic suggestions, and that most IPD diagnoses are made by a few specialist psychiatrists. ("Dissociative Identity Disorder - PMC - PubMed Central (PMC)") They also claim that most ICD diagnoses are made by psychiatrists. They came to this conclusion after discovering that there was slight difference in symptoms that differentiated the two diagnoses. Instead, they found what they called a "syndrome" of symptoms that can occur in people with unstable personalities, including borderline personality disorder . They concluded that DID does not have a clear clinical picture, laboratory tests are unreliable, cannot be clearly differentiated from other diseases, does not have a clear natural history, and does not have a familial pattern. That same year, North and colleagues concluded that the diagnosis was "really" unconfirmed, although they began to "believe" in its existence. This conclusion was reached after enormous efforts were made to answer this question by empirically reviewing the literature. "Available information currently does not sufficiently justify the validity of DID as a separate diagnosis", but this in no way proves or disproves the concept. After that, Spira¹⁵ edited a book describing the various treatment options and written by proponents of the existence of DID. Researchers Loewenstein and Bliss found that dissociative identity disorder (DID) exists and is spontaneous . autohypnotic concluded that the symptoms are essential for the phenomenology of DID. Gelinas

has documented autohypnotic and post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms in individuals with dissociative identity disorder (DID) .

These symptoms were likely a reaction to childhood sexual abuse. Spiegel and Rosenfeld¹⁹ believed that trauma -related PTSD symptoms were at the core of ICD and attributed the " spontaneous age regression" (toward a younger alter) seen in ICD patients to early trauma. They also believed that DID was caused by early trauma . According to research led by Horevitz and Braun , a chart review revealed that seventy percent of patients diagnosed with "multiple personality disorder (DPD)" would most likely meet the criteria for borderline personality disorder. They concluded that dissociative identity disorder was a separate entity but was overdiagnosed as they found added individuals who could not be identified as such. Patients diagnosed with IPD Structured Clinical Interview (SCID) for DSM Disorders, Structured Interview for DSM-III-R Personality Disorders (SIDP-R), Dissociative Disorder Interview Schedule (DDIS), Beck Depression, Beck Hopelessness and Dissociative Experiences Scale (DES) and Shipley Institute of Living scale . They discovered that 64 percent of patients diagnosed with DID meet the criteria for borderline personality disorder but met most of the criteria for borderline personality disorder, even among those who did not meet all criteria for borderline personality disorder .

On the other hand, Horevitz and Braun discovered that one-third of individuals previously diagnosed with IPD on Axis I did not meet the criteria for any Axis II disorder , according to the assessment scales . This was the conclusion the researchers came to. It is noteworthy that DES was found to be higher in ICD patients than in other subjects. Coons et al . concluded that dissociative identity disorder (DID) is a " syndrome " that occurs in people with personality disorders , particularly borderline personality disorder. They also concluded that DID and borderline personality disorder are on the same spectrum of character disorders, and that DID stand for the more severe end of the spectrum. They argued that dissociative identity disorder develops from a base of borderline features. Insomnia, sexual dysfunction, anger, suicidality, self-mutilation, substance and alcohol abuse, anxiety, paranoia, somatization, dissociation, mood changes and pathological changes in relationships are some of the symptoms associated with dissociative identity disorder (DID). The authors argued that the multiplicity of symptoms associated with DID supports their view. (“Dissociative Identity Disorder - PMC - PubMed Central (PMC)”)

traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) because of prolonged and repetitive trauma . To learn more about the definition of Alters and Alternates , go here. Watkins and Watkins make it clear that there is a difference between ego states and alters, although some people refer to the changes found in DID as ego states. In their understanding, the ego state is " an orderly system of action and experience, the parts of which are connected by some common principles but separated from other such states by barriers that are more or less permeable." The alters in DID "have their own identity, which includes a center of initiative and experience; they have a characteristic self-representation that may differ from how the patient is generally viewed or perceived; they have their own autobiographical memory and distinguish what they distinguish." they understand that they have their own actions and experiences from what is done and experienced by other ego states."

Watkins and others distinguish the concept of alter from ego states. The effects of exposure to situations of extreme ambivalence and abuse in early childhood, coping with a form of elaborate denial for the child to believe that the event has happened to someone else , are often attributed to the development of dissociative identity disorder. The " solution" to a major trauma in a child's life at that time may be a dissociated identity. This is due to the life stage a child is in where imaginary friends "exist". PTSD symptoms , on the other hand, are more likely to present themselves when the traumatic event occurs later in childhood or in the person's adult life. Severe maltreatment of children, a chaotic and disoriented attachment style, as well as a lack of social and family support seem to precede the development of dissociative identity disorder (DID). The tendency to separate appears to be due to a pathogenic family structure as well as an attachment problem bought early in the child's life. This seems to be the case regardless of the individual's initial temperament or genetics. The authoritarian and rigid parenting approach often adopted by these patients was ironically accompanied by a reversal of the traditional parent-child dynamic. Blizard hypothesized that children displaying a disorganized or disoriented attachment pattern may be resolving conflicting representations of parental behavior and that different attachment patterns may be implicated in various personalities in ICD . Blizard also hypothesized that these children may be parsing conflicting representations of parental behavior.

7. Conclusion

chaos shown in a DID patient's attachment pattern is particularly striking considering some recent discoveries in neuroscience about this condition. In one study, a subsample of DID patients showed abnormal interest distribution on the Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale-Revised (WAIS-R) verbal subtests. This variability was attributed to subtle neuropsychological deficits in the memory/difficulty factor like that seen in attention deficit disorder (ADD) . In another study, patients with DID show a prepulse inhibition (PPI) in the acoustic startle reflex . This suggests that DID patients have maladaptive attentional processes when working at a controlled level, but not when working at an automatic level of pre-attention. Patients with other dissociative disorders did not show this PPI. Patients with DID have an elevated level of alertness, resulting in decreased startle reflexes and increased PPI. This response is an intentional procedure that diverts attention from stimuli perceived as unpleasant or potentially dangerous . The authors concluded that an abnormal pattern of voluntary attention processes may be a hallmark of DID . A third study found that patients with DID have decreased bilateral regional cerebral blood flow (rCBF) in regions of the orbitofrontal cortex (like that seen in attention deficit disorder) and increased rCBF in the median and superior frontal regions . The clear degree of compartmentalization of learned items has been found in a memory study conducted on subjects to depend on the degree to which information is interpreted and stored in ways that convey a unique meaning to the alter or "personality state." A diagnosis of DID was made by Nissen et al.³³. This was discovered in a memory study conducted on subjects diagnosed with DID. They concluded that "implicit" memories can be most effectively stored and retrieved during different states of behavioral awareness, and this is the first time they occur. On the other hand, one identity was able to detect neutral expressions bought by the other identity. In addition, memories of seemingly neutral expressions transmitted by auditory input but visually recovered showed inter-identity memory transfer. This was the case when the memory was visually invoked. Huntjens et al. Clinical models of amnesia in ICD should not have deficiencies for emotionally neutral content. Compared with healthy people, one study that did not exclude patients who also suffered from PTSD symptoms found that the volume of the hippocampus was 19.2 percent smaller in patients with DID, and the volume of the amygdala was 31.6 percent smaller. In another study, trauma -exposed subjects with PTSD symptoms but no DID have significant impairment in cognition, as well as significant amygdala and hippocampus , compared with controls. This contrasted with trauma-exposed patients in the same study who had normal amygdala and hippocampus as well as normal

cognition, had symptoms of DID but did not have PTSD. 38 Further work is needed to decide whether the symptoms of dissociative identity disorder (DID) play a neurologically protective, defensive role by creating a neuroprotective environment that improves the neurotoxic consequences of traumatic stress .

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